

FEATURES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UNIVERSITIES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6717201>

Saidov Shakhrukh-Mirzo
Kokand University, PhD student

In the modern socio-economic context, concepts such as 'regional university', 'industrial university' are becoming increasingly conditional and require change, because if a university engages in a narrow industry, it will be 'doomed' to decline and lag behind. As a result of the analysis of the national projects "Education" and "Science", it was concluded that they include important events in which regional and sectoral universities can participate. However, they are characterized by the presence of low starting positions and underdeveloped scientific potential, which reduces the chances of winning competitions. Thus, we are dealing with a gap in the quality of education with leading universities. The above sets tasks to increase the internal capacity of universities to increase their competitiveness.

Today, it is important to continue the formation of such a communication system in science and increase the willingness of the economy to innovate in various fields, as the mechanisms of support and incentives for national projects strengthen the interest of businesses and state companies to participate in research projects and programs of higher education. aimed at full support.

In this regard, it is necessary to give enterprises the opportunity to obtain all the real information necessary for the organization of interaction from open sources, reflecting the essence of research and development currently underway in universities to make investments. Thus, it is important to introduce approaches to the implementation of federal projects and the use of various indicators in the evaluation of the activities of universities and research organizations. The positions of universities in different rankings are important. Over the past few years, the ratings of educational institutions have become a sought-after and important attribute of the market of educational services not only in Russia but also in the world.

It is this tool that shapes social reality and allows for the creation of an appropriate image of specific universities. Given the goals and objectives of national projects, prestige in national and international education markets is a key factor on which a university's competitive success depends in general [2]. Ratings play a key role in this process: as the university takes the lead in both global and national rankings, its attractiveness to applicants, employers, investors and the state will increase significantly.

To date, there are certain trends in higher education to create such models that provide the necessary relationship between universities and the state, business structures and society, without which it will be difficult to occupy sufficiently high positions. Various forms of cooperation, such as university-based science and innovation clusters, network forms of interaction (e.g., "barrier-free business incubators"), etc., have their own characteristics and are based on the modernization of traditional networks. The development of the

economy is to contribute to the transformation of relevant developments into a key vector of economic growth of the local economy in the context of "digitization".

The author of this study is convinced that universities with high intellectual potential and shaping their internal ecosystem can provide competitive advantages that allow them not only to create unique competencies, but also to increase assets by following the path of growth and development [3]. In this process, universities play an important role in shaping their value system, whose attributes include the following indicators: university ranking, its prestige and prestige (i.e., the presence of a particular brand); high quality of education, level of research, as well as monitoring of knowledge, technology and so on. Thus, it becomes clear that a university with a well-known and already formed rating is competitive.

It should be noted that in most of the currently known rankings, the main indicators of the efficiency and quality of university activities are the effectiveness of their activities in the following key areas: education and science, internationalization and commercialization. However, despite the obvious similarity of the ratings, they differ, as a rule, by the set and number of indicators evaluated, as well as the system of weighted coefficients formed, and so on.

In line with modern requirements, modern universities continue to change, new models are emerging, which require a change in the rankings, which allows universities to draw objective conclusions about the implementation of their tasks [4]. In particular, there should be a modified assessment of the impact of universities on the economy, and

this should only take into account and use relevant information about the 'achievements' of universities.

Access to different rankings allows you to search and find the balance you need, but the process should end on its own and not become a race. Thus, a rating is a type of window that can more or less adequately reflect the current reality over a period of time. In our view, it is more important to understand the trends in the development of higher education in the digital economy and to form priorities based on the specific characteristics of the university, as well as to act consistently along the path envisaged by the thought strategy. The practice of evaluating the performance of universities, which took first place in the ranking, allowed to identify their main differences: the ability to form responses to rapidly changing reality problems in the context of uncertainty and mobility of the external environment; key participants in the process of modernization of the domestic economy, the contribution to improving the quality and standard of living of citizens.

The forms of development of social entrepreneurship of universities are due to the fact that this type of activity is necessary at the current stage of the country and aims to increase the growth rate of the national economy. However, on the one hand, many social problems have not been solved in our country, on the other hand, because there are not many people willing to implement social projects, universities can become a pillar of the state in solving the social problems of its citizens. To create the necessary conditions for the development of the institution of social entrepreneurship in the regions through the implementation of the "social mission".

References

1. Наукометрические показатели вуза : метод. рекомендации [Текст] / сост. Г.Л. Шаматонова, Н.Г. Живаев. –Яросл гос. ун-т. – Ярославль :ЯрГУ. – 2012. –48 с.

2. Шаркова, А.В. Роль высших учебных заведений в развитии инновационного предпринимательства в Российской Федерации [Текст] // Экономика и предпринимательство. – 2014. – № 6. – С. 791–794.

3. Пугач, В.Ф. Рейтинги вузов: международный и российский подходы [Текст] / В.Ф. Пугач, М.Э. Жуковская // Высшее образование в России. – 2012. – № 8/9. – С. 15–25.

4. Карпов, А. Современный университет как драйвер экономического роста: модели и миссии [Текст] // Вопросы экономики. – 2017. – № 3. – С. 58–76.